

Synthesis and Spectral Study of 2-Phenyl-4-(3'-N-N-Dimethylaminomethyl-4'-Hydroxy)-Anilinoquinazoline Derivatives

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2-Phenyl-4-(3'-disubstitutedaminomethyl-4'-hydroxy)-anilinoquinazolines and their 6-chloro, 7-chloro and 6-methoxy derivatives have been prepared by condensation of the corresponding 4-chloroquinazoline with 4-hydroxyaniline followed by Mannich reaction, and also with 3-N-N-disubstitutedaminomethyl-4-hydroxyaniline. UV and IR spectra of these compounds have been reported.

THE work presented in this communication deals with the synthesis and spectral characterisation of the title compounds. It forms an extension of the two papers presented in this series by Patel and his co-workers.^{1,2} These compounds can be considered to be potential antimalarials on the basis of the similarity of their structures with the chloroquin³. However, paucity of the material has prevented the testing of the possible antimalarial properties of these compounds.

2-Phenyl-4-chloroquinazoline(I) and its 7-chloro(II), 6-chloro(III) and 6-methoxy derivatives(IV) were prepared by reacting the required 2-phenyl-4-oxoquinazoline derivative with a mixture of phosphorus oxychloride and phosphorus pentoxide. These 2-phenyl-4-chloroquinazolines unlike their 2-alkyl analogues could be preserved under dry conditions in closed container for a long time.

2-Phenyl-4-chloroquinazoline(I), was condensed with 4-hydroxyaniline in ethanol at 80°, affording 2-phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy) anilinoquinazoline(V) in nearly quantitative yield. The condensation of 2-phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy) anilinoquinazoline(V) with paraformaldehyde and diethylamine afforded 2-phenyl-4-(3'-diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxy)-anilinoquinazoline(VI). The other compound of the series were prepared similarly using appropriate secondary amine and 2-phenyl-4-chloroquinazoline derivative.

All the analogues of VI were prepared by an alternate method comprising a reaction between required 2-phenyl-4-chloroquinazoline derivative and appropriate 3-N, N-disubstituted aminomethyl-4-hydroxyaniline in presence of dilute aqueous HCl. The yield in both the methods were nearly quantitative.

TABLE 1—2-PHENYL-4-(3'N,N-DISUBSTITUTED AMINOMETHYL-4'-HYDROXYANILINO) QUINAZOLINE DERIVATIVES

Compound	R*	R ₁ [†]	R ₂ [†]	Formula	†m.p. °C	N%		λmax(nm) (log ε)					
						Found	Calc.						
V	H	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	230	13.26	13.42	252,	275,	341	(4.60,	4.28,	4.20)
VI	a	H	H	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₄ O	115	14.15	14.07	251,	276,	346	(4.70,	4.35,	4.29)
VII	b	H	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O	126	15.14	15.00	251,	275,	344	(4.60,	4.37,	4.27)
VIII	c	H	H	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O	124	13.50	13.66	252,	275,	344	(4.55,	4.22,	4.13)
IX	H	H	Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ OCl	241	12.01	11.81	255,	280,	348	(4.57,	4.32,	4.12)
X	a	H	Cl	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ N ₄ OCl	135	12.95	12.79	250,	286,	343	(4.51,	4.33,	4.06)
XI	b	H	Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₄ OCl	170	13.72	13.85	251,	282,	350	(4.56,	4.29,	4.02)
XII	c	H	Cl	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₄ OCl	205	12.34	12.60	252,	282,	352	(4.59,	4.31,	4.14)
XIII	H	Cl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₃ OCl	205	11.68	11.81	255,	281,	354	(4.66,	4.28,	4.15)
XIV	a	Cl	H	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ N ₄ OCl	152	12.87	12.79	254,	280,	350	(4.66,	4.28,	4.18)
XV	b	Cl	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₄ OCl	170	13.32	13.85	253,	280,	349	(4.63,	4.29,	4.12)
XVI	c	Cl	H	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₄ OCl	178	12.45	12.60	254,	280,	350	(4.61,	4.23,	4.13)
XVII	H	OMe	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	210	12.12	12.25	d: 251,	285,	352	(4.60,	4.27,	4.23)
								e: 250,	290,	365	(4.66,	4.21,	4.10)
								f: 271,	310,	372	(4.56,	4.08,	4.23)
XVIII	a	OMe	H	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₂	125	13.27	13.08	d: 250,	280,	355	(4.61,	4.30,	4.24)
								e: 240,	300,	371	(4.61,	4.26,	4.20)
								f: 272,	315,	372	(4.55,	4.02,	4.21)
XIX	b	OMe	H	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂	154	14.00	14.18	d: 250,	285,	355	(4.60,	4.27,	4.13)
								e: 250,	295,	366	(4.57,	4.21,	3.72)
								f: 270,	310,	366	(4.49,	4.04,	4.17)
XX	c	OMe	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₂	120	12.73	12.93	d: 249,	285,	351	(4.55,	4.22,	4.20)
								e: 250,	300,	363	(4.61,	3.13,	3.98)
								f: 271,	310,	372	(4.52,	4.09,	4.22)

R*

a = -CH₂N(Et)₂, b = -CH₂N(Me)₂, c = -CH₂-N

† all m.ps. are uncorrected.

d = Neutral, e = basic, f = acidic.

The uv spectra of 2- and 4-oxoquinazolines have been reported earlier by other workers at different pH 's^{4,5,6}. These studies and other evidences reveal that 4-oxoquinazolinone like 4-quinolinones and 4-pyridinones exist mostly in the keto form in the solid state and in solution. It has been reported that 4-aminoquinolines, 4-aminopyrimidines and other related compounds exist mostly in the imino form.^{7,8,9} The latter investigation, however, has shown that it is not correct. The X-ray analysis^{10,11} and basicity measurements, have shown that 4-aminopyrimidine exists in the amino form. UV spectral characteristics of 4-aminoquinazolines have not been reported so far. The uv spectra of 4-anilinoquinazolines V to XX have been studied in $10^{-5}M$ solution in ethanol-water mixtures containing 80% of ethanol. The spectral data are reported in Table-1. Examination of these data reveals that the uv spectra of all the compounds are very nearly similar and comprise three bands around 250, 275 and 340-350 nm respectively and their extinction coefficient decrease in the same order.

In the methoxy series the uv spectra of XVII, XVIII, XIX and XX were studied in neutral, acidic and basic media. The spectral data are presented in Table-1. These data reveal that the compounds XVII to XX have nearly similar uv spectra in neutral and in basic media. However, in the acidic medium all the three bands have shifted towards the longer wavelength indicating increased conjugation. On this much evidence it is not possible to draw any definite conclusion about the tautomeric form of these compounds; the uv spectral data suggest the possibility that the compound exists mostly in the amino form. Had it not existed mostly in the amino form, it would have been difficult to explain such a large shift in the positions of the bands in acidic medium.

The ir spectra of some quinazolines have been reported earlier by other workers.^{12,13} The ir spectra of all the compounds V to XX were recorded in nujol. The spectral data shows almost all the characteristic features reported of these compounds. Some of the characteristic features of the spectra are noted here. The ir data indicated that all the compounds exhibit a sharp band around 3435 cm^{-1} (NH), a weak band around

$1640\text{-}1690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to C=N stretching. All these compounds exhibit a group of four bands in the region $1613\text{ to }1471\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of a quinazolinone skeleton. However, these features would not throw any light on the nature of the tautomeric form in which the compound exists.

Experimental

*R*₁, *R*₂-Substituted 2-phenyl-4-chloroquinazolines I, II, III and IV: Following procedure for the preparation of I, II, III and IV was used.

A mixture of 2-phenyl-3H-4-oxoquinazolin-2(1H)-one (12.0 g), PCl₅ (15.0 g) and POCl₃ (60 ml) was refluxed at 130° for 4 hrs. Excess of POCl₃ was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The residue was decomposed by ice and saturated solution of NaHCO₃. The mixture was extracted with ether several times. After drying the combined ether extracts (Na₂SO₄) the solvent was removed to furnish 2-phenyl-4-chloroquinazolinone I, C₁₄H₉N₂Cl. It was crystallized from ether-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1) in yellowish needles, m. p. 124°, lit.² m. p. 124°-25°.

2-Phenyl-4,7-dichloroquinazolinone II, m. p. 135°, Yellow needles from ether-pet. ether,

Found : N, 10.35, Calc. for C₁₄H₇N₂Cl₂ : N, 10.22.

2-Phenyl-4,6-dichloroquinazolinone III, m.p. 147°, Yellow needles from ether, N% Found, 10.35, Calcd. for C₁₄H₇N₂Cl₂ : 10.22.

2-Phenyl-4-chloro-6-methoxyquinazolinone IV: The required 2-phenyl-3H-6-methoxy-4-oxoquinazolinone was prepared as follows :

A finely powdered mixture of N-benzoyl-p-anisidine (10 g), urethane (10 g) and P₂O₅ (30 g) was heated in a R. B. flask at 170°-80° for 3 hrs. The mixture was cooled and treated with ice-cold water, and was made slightly basic with NaOH. The solid product was filtered, washed with H₂O and dried. It was crystallized from acetic acid to give 2-phenyl-3H-6-methoxy-4-oxoquinazolinone, m. p. 262°, (8 g),

N%, Found 11.2, Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂N₂O₂ : 11.1.

2-Phenyl-4-chloro-6-methoxyquinazoline IV, was then prepared as described under the general procedure. It was crystallized from ether, m. p. 135°.

N%, Found, 10.42. Calcd. for
C₁₅H₁₁N₂OCl : 10.35.

2-Phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy) anilinoquinazoline V: A solution of 2-phenyl-4-chloroquinazoline (2.1 g) and 4-hydroxyaniline (1.0 g) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 45 min, alcohol was distilled off and remaining residue was basified with ammonia solution, The solid product was crystallized from ethanol to furnish, V, m. p. 230°, (2.7 g), N% : Found 13.25, Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₅N₃O : 13.42.

Mannich reaction on 2-phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy) anilinoquinazoline V. Formation of 2-phenyl-4-(3'-diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxy) anilinoquinazoline VI: A mixture of 2-phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy) anilinoquinazoline (1.0 g); ethanol (10 ml), paraformaldehyde (0.1 g) and diethylamine (0.5 ml) was refluxed at 100° for 2 hrs. The alcohol was removed by distillation, residue was treated with water and the solid was filtered, washed and dried. Recrystallization from aq. ethanol furnished, VI, m. p. 115°, (0.9 g).

By this procedure compounds, VII, VIII, X to XII, XIV to XVI, and XVIII to XX were prepared using appropriate secondary amine.

2-Phenyl-4-(3'-diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxy) anilinoquinazoline VI; alternate procedure: A mixture of 3-diethyl-aminomethyl-4-hydroxyacetanilide¹ (1.2 g) and HCl (10 ml, 20%) was refluxed for about an hour. The cooled mixture was treated with 20% dilute alkali so that the mixture remains just acidic to congo red. It was not necessary to isolate the base. To this solution, 2-phenyl 4-chloroquinazoline (2.0 g) was added and the mixture was heated on water bath for an hour.

The reaction mixture then basified by adding excess of ammonia solution. The separated base, VI, was crystallized from aq. ethanol, m, p. 115°.

All other compounds were also prepared by this method.

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